

Magnetic Microfluidic Platform for *E. coli* Detection in Water Samples

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Bacterial detection is of utmost priority for water quality control since microbial contamination threatens the health and well-being of wildlife, livestock, and human populations and can lead to serious illness and even death. Rapid and multiplexed measurement of such water-borne pathogens is vital and the challenge is to instantly detect in these liquid samples (in real time and at low cost) different types of pathogens with high sensitivity and specificity. Traditional detection methods such as culture techniques/plate counting or molecular techniques and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs) which are highly specific and sensitive are also slow, expensive and often lack the capability of multiplex detection.

In this work, we propose a novel biosensing system (Fig. 1) in which the pathogens are labelled with streptavidin coated magnetic markers (MPs). Video microscopy in combination with a particle tracking software are used for their detection. The sample containing the bacteria is mixed with commercially available MPs (Dynabeads Streptavidin MyOne T1) and suspended in DI water. If *E. coli* bacteria are present they will bind to the surface of these MPs forming compounds (MLPs –magnetically labelled bacteria). When the liquid containing the MLPs is introduced into the developed, microfluidic platform the MLPs are accelerated towards the outlet by means of a magnetic field gradient generated by integrated microconductors, which are sequentially switched ON and OFF by a microcontroller (Fig. 2). The velocities of the MLPs and that of reference MPs, suspended in the same liquid in a parallel reference microfluidic channel, are calculated and compared in real time by a digital camera mounted on a conventional optical microscope in combination with a particle trajectory tracking software. The MLPs will be slower than the reference MPs due to the enhanced Stokes' drag force exerted on them, resulting from their greater volume and altered hydrodynamic shape. A registered difference in velocity indicates the presence of the *E. coli* bacteria.

Figure 1: The developed biosensing system; Microfluidic platform connected to the microcontroller underneath the microscope.

Figure 2: Working principle; Picture A represents the forces acting on an individual MP. Picture B represents the differently sized MP-*E. coli* compounds with various migration velocities v . The fluid in which the MPs are suspended is static ($u=0$). Their motion depends on the amount of *E. coli* attachment.